

Verification report

Document

File name	Paper_3_DE_Replica.tex+(Replica+Symmetry+Breaking)-sign.pdf
Hash value	hTyErKma3Fvo24tBRIPmdmE3JNT1bexKOMfy7/Dacrk= (SHA-256, Base64-encoded)
Size	223.48 kB
Type	PDF signature (PAdES-B)

Signature/Seal

Checks

Time of signature/seal and verification resp. (UTC)	2025-12-11T23:53:15Z
Signature/Seal	The verification of the signature/seal value was successful.
Qualified certificate	There is a certificate chain up to a trusted root certificate. Each certificate of this chain was valid at the given time.

Further information

Type of signature/seal	PAdES-B
Type of signature algorithm	SHA256withECDSA
The Signature covers the following Byterange/s	0,182706,190900,37946

Properties of the PDF signature

Reason for signature creation	Signaturpruefung unter http://www.signaturpruefung.gv.at
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Signatory/Creator of seal

Name	Stefan Heinz Horvath
Country	AT
Serial number	dec.: 896347576905, hex.: d0:b2:7a:9a:49

Issuer

Name	a-sign-premium-mobile-05
Organizational unit	a-sign-premium-mobile-05
Organization	A-Trust Ges. f. Sicherheitssysteme im elektr. Datenverkehr GmbH
Country	AT

Certificate

Serialnumber	dec.: 2057053933, hex.: 7a:9c:26:ed
Quality	qualified certificate (Source: TSL), secure signature-creation device (Source: certificate)
Validity period	valid from 2021-05-27T14:37:14Z to 2026-05-27T14:37:14Z The given time of verification is within the validity period.
Key Usage	digitalSignature, nonRepudiation
Certification policy statement	http://www.a-trust.at/docs/cp/a-sign-premium-mobile

Trusted service

Issuer Country	AT
ServiceTypeStatus	http://uri.etsi.org/TrstSvc/TrustedList/Svcstatus/granted
ServiceTypeIdentifier	http://uri.etsi.org/TrstSvc/Svctype/CA/QC
Additional Service Information	http://uri.etsi.org/TrstSvc/TrustedList/SvcInfoExt/ForeSignatures http://uri.etsi.org/TrstSvc/TrustedList/SvcInfoExt/ForeSignatures

Note: Under the Austrian Signature Law, Austrian certification service providers that issue qualified certificates are under supervision of Telekom-Control Commission. Its branch Austrian Regulatory Authority for Broadcasting and Telecommunications (RTR) offers this signature verification service. Electronic signatures based on certificates issued by foreign certification service providers offer an automated verification; in that case no guarantees whatsoever for a correct technical interpretation of such foreign certificates can be given.

